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POSTER PRESENTATIONS

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS IN THE KIDNEY OF FETUSES WITH DOWN SYNDROME

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Introduction: Children with Down syndrome (DS) have five times more renal and urinary tract abnormalities than in healthy population. The data on renal disease in adults is sparse, although there are an increasing number of chronic renal failure in adults with DS. The aim of this study is to contribute to a better understanding of the morphological changes that can occur in fetuses with DS, which can be the reason for the occurrence of renal abnormalities in this population postnatal.

Materials and methods: Fetal kidneys collected during autopsy and 39 subjects were included. Subjects were divided into two groups: fetuses with DS (n = 17) with a gestational age ranging from 9 up to 33 weeks, and healthy fetuses (N-fetuses, n = 22) with a same gestational age. Paraffin blocks were used and stained with standard H&E method. Using microscope and computer programme, the nephrogenic and maturation zone thickness, the area and diameter of the glomerular tuft, the area and diameter of glomeruli were morphometrically analyzed.

Results: Undertaken statistical analyses determined statistically significant difference in glomerular area and diameter of glomerular tuft between fetuses with DS and N-fetuses ($p < 0,05$). Glomerular area and diameter of glomerular tuft are bigger in younger

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gestational ages in DS fetuses, while by ageing it lag behind glomeruli in control groups ($p < 0,05$).

Conclusion: The morphological differences we registered between these two groups of subjects suggest delayed renal maturation in fetuses with DS. These changes in the glomerular structure may result in a nephron deficit and may have significant implications in development of renal diseases later in life.

Keywords: Down syndrome, nephrogenesis, glomerular development, renal disease